

Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings

EN-TRACK Dissemination and Communication Plan and Associated Material

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BOF	Building Owners Forum
FIF	Financial Institutions Forum
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

The communication and dissemination (C&D) efforts described in this deliverable cover activities such as participation in and presentations given at events; webinars organised in the scope of EN-TRACK; peer-reviewed scientific papers; non-peer-reviewed articles; press releases; collaboration with other H2020 projects; newsletters and communication materials sent to the EN-TRACK stakeholder community; videos and other marketing materials.

Furthermore, the online presence of the project is addressed. The deliverable describes the development and the status of the EN-TRACK website, the social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube) and the EN-TRACK presence at the ENLIT Europe platform. It also accounts for the use of the Zenodo platform to ensure open access to all public deliverables.

The deliverable describes how the KPIs related to communication and dissemination activities are continuously monitored, and also gives an overview of the status as of M15. The overall picture is that EN-TRACK is very well on track with KPIs related to the online presence, the publication of articles and the presence at events.

To summarise the content and the state of progress of EN-TRACK's C&D:

- In the period M1-M15 of the project, the dissemination and communication efforts have successfully facilitated internal and external interactions that helped create awareness around the project.
- EN-TRACK is very well on track and performing well in relation to most KPIs. For the remainder, mitigation actions have been planned and a roadmap created to ensure that all KPIs will be reached and to support the exploitation potential of the project.

1 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a summary of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken in the period M1-M15. The activities undertaken in this period build upon the communication and dissemination strategy outlined in the *Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.2)*. This deliverable follows up on the actions and provides an overview of the KPIs related to the communication and dissemination activities.

Following this introduction, section 2 provides an update on the communication and dissemination activities completed in the period M1-M15. There is a brief description of each activity accompanied by relevant numbers such as views, language, and media outlets.

Section 3 describes the development of the project's online presence. It reports on the website traffic, social media activities and additional online presence.

Section 4 presents a complete overview of the status of the different KPIs related to the communication and dissemination activities of the project.

2 Communication and dissemination activities

This section gives an update of the communication and dissemination activities, including presentations at events, the advisory board activities, webinars, scientific and non-scientific articles, public deliverables, Horizon 2020 project synergies and marketing collateral such as videos, newsletters, and other communication via the online stakeholder community as well as visual communication material such as posters and flyers.

2.1 Events

The presence at different events is crucial for the engagement of EN-TRACK stakeholders and a key part of the dissemination activities targeting peers. The KPIs focus on I) *events with EN-TRACK active presence* (section 2.1.1), defined as events where consortium partners are engaging in discussions with peers or are promoting the project and II) *events with EN-TRACK presentations* (section 2.1.2) which is defined as

events where consortium partners are registered as presenting partners, e.g., with a PowerPoint presentation, a poster session, or a booth at a fair.

2.1.1 Events with the EN-TRACK active presence

Table 1 provides an overview of events with active presence, the active consortium partner, the date and the number of attendees.

Event	Action	Presenting partner	Date	No. of attendees
EE-EU Regulations and Funding	Promoting EN-TRACK	EnEffect	27/4/21	50
Energy Digitalisation Taskforce Launch Webinar	Highlighted EN-TRACK and possible EU-UK collaboration on Energy Digitalisation Activities	EP Group	12/05/21	300-400

Table 1

2.1.2 Events with EN-TRACK presentations

Table 2 provides an overview of events with EN-TRACK presentations, the presenting partner(s), the dates, and the number of attendees.

Event	Title	Presenting partner	Date	No. of attendees
Sustainable Places	Financing the Energy Transition, paper session	Joule Assets Europe / CIMNE-BEE Group	29/09/21	20
International Conference for Sustainable Development	Poster session	Joule Assets Europe	20-21/09/21	2057

Event	Title	Presenting partner	Date	No. of attendees
Webinar on Energy Transition	Presentation of EN-TRACK	ICAEN	13/05/21	110
Consultancy meeting on municipal energy management	Presentation of EN-TRACK and BOF	EnEffect	16/11/21	20
Sustainable Energy Investment Forum	Presentation of EN-TRACK	EnEffect	19/05/21	150
Climate and Energy Days, hybrid event by Gabrovo municipality	Presentation of EN-TRACK	EnEffect	24/06/21	105
nZEB in Smolyan	Presentation of EN-TRACK	EnEffect	21/10/21	40
Municipal energy managers training	Presentation of EN-TRACK	EnEffect	29/11/21	200

Table 2

2.2 Advisory Board

The main reasons for the advisory board are to benefit from expertise outside of the EN-TRACK consortium and to also foster wider support for the EN-TRACK platform through the additional networking capacity of these relevant peers. The advisory board is addressed through special meetings of which an overview is provided in Table 3.

Event	Action	Presenting partner	Date	No. of attendees
First advisory board meeting	Promotion & feedback	CIMNE	19/05/21	8
Second advisory board meeting	Promotion & feedback	CIMNE	01/06/21	2

Table 3

2.3 Webinars

As per the Grant Agreement, EN-TRACK will host 5 webinars during the project period. So far, one introductory webinar has been executed. Details can be seen in Table 4.

Title	Partners	Date	No. of attendees	No. of view of recordings
Introductory webinar	CIMNE-BEE Group & Steven Fawkes/EP Group and EEFIG representant	26 May 2021	40	44

Table 4

2.4 Articles (non-peer reviewed)

Table 5 provides an overview of articles targeting the general public, that is, non-peer reviewed. The responsible partner, the date, the link and a summary are also provided.

Title	Partner	Journal & link	Date	Summary
Increasing Private	GECO Global	EN-TRACK website	Jan. 2021	Interview with project coordinator about the

Investments in Energy Efficiency Refurbishments	& CIMNE-BEE Group			perspectives and expected benefits of the EN-TRACK platform.
EN-TRACK Project	CIMNE-BEE Group	BuildUp	Oct. 2020	Introduction and description of the EN-TRACK project
How to characterize energy use in buildings?	CIMNE-BEE Group & GECO Global	BuildUp	Sept. 2021	Promotion and brief non-technical introduction to research published by EN-TRACK (see section 2.5).

Table 5

2.5 Scientific papers (peer-reviewed)

Table 6 provides an overview of peer-reviewed scientific articles. The responsible partner, the date, the link and a summary are also provided.

Title	Partner	Journal & link	Date	Summary
Baseline Energy Use Modelling and Characterization in Tertiary Buildings Using an Interpretable Bayesian Linear Regression Methodology	CIMNE-BEE Group	energies	Sept. 2021	It assesses how interpretable and scalable data-driven methodologies can provide predictions for energy use in buildings.

Title	Partner	Journal & link	Date	Summary
The EN-TRACK Energy Efficiency Performance Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings. Data Model Development	CIMNE-BEE Group	Environmental Sciences Proceedings: The 9th Annual Edition of Sustainable Places (SP 2021)	Nov. 2021	The paper focuses on the methodology and the semantic technologies used in the development of the platform's data model.

Table 6

2.6 Public deliverables

Open access to public deliverables is granted by uploading to Zenodo, the open science online platform. The visibility of the research available in these deliverables is supported by all public deliverables being promoted on the project's social media channels and the website. Table 7 provides an overview of the public deliverables, the number of views and downloads.

Title	Partner	No. Of views	No. Of downloads	Date
EN-TRACK Data Management Plan (D8.1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5148260	CIMNE	20	15	30/07/2021
EN-TRACK overall requirements and data model (D1.1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5148241	EnergyPro	107	49	30/07/2021
Measurement and verification procedures for energy efficiency investments (D1.4) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5846731	EnergyPro	0	0	13/01/2022

Table 7

2.7 Horizon 2020 project synergies

EN-TRACK aims at creating connections with other initiatives and projects funded by the EU. EN-TRACK has joined a group of Horizon 2020 sister projects which currently consists of SENSEI, NOVICE, TripleA, LAUNCH, AmBIENce, RenOnBill, X-tendo, U-Cert, Quest, FrESCO, EN-TRACK and DEESME. In addition to presenting EN-TRACK to the sister projects at a meeting held in January 2021, the sister projects collaborate on increasing online visibility by liking and sharing posts and updates as well as sharing relevant surveys with the different stakeholder communities.

EN-TRACK was also presented by EnEffect at the QualdEPC webinar that took place on 04/02/2021. Considering the very early stage of the project, the focus was on the project goals and the approach to be used for the elaboration of the EN-TRACK platform. A short survey including 3 questions (Q1: What data would you like to receive from such a platform? Q2: Do you think that building owners and financing institutions from Bulgaria will benefit from such a platform? Q3: Would you take advantage of this type of platform?) was initiated to get initial feedback from the participants.

2.8 Newsletters and communication with the online stakeholder community

The online stakeholder community now consists of 87 external subscribers, that is, persons who are not members of the project consortium. The community is governed via Mailchimp which allows to segment the audience based on their stakeholder category, which they are invited to fill out when signing up. This allows us to target them with specific information. In addition to promoting the community on social media, subscribers have been invited by the consortium partners using targeted invitations (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

During this first reporting period, EN-TRACK has sent two newsletters to its online stakeholder community. The community is set up via MailChimp and has currently 91 subscribers.

The [first newsletter](#) was sent in M9 and reached an open rate of 33.7%. The [second newsletter](#) was sent in M13 with an open rate of 30.8%. As the KPI for the open rate of newsletters decided in the Grant Agreement is 50%, this is not good enough. However, compared to the average open rate for newsletters which is 21.33%, [measured by MailChimp](#)¹, the EN-TRACK newsletter is performing very well. This is supported by the

¹ The analysis of open rates by MailChimp was accessed on 27 Jan. 2022 at <https://mailchimp.com/resources/email-marketing-benchmarks/>

detailed analysis of the open rates performed by MailChimp which breaks down the open rates depending on industries. Relevant for the EN-TRACK stakeholder community are the open rates for the categories of “Business and Finance” and “Construction” which is respectively 21.56% and 21.77%. Hence, it is not unjustified to define the open rate of the newsletters as a success. This is also supported by the open rates of other materials sent to the community which includes [an invitation](#) to the first EN-TRACK webinar that reached an open rate of 56.6% and, an invitation to a segmented audience of building owners and operators who were invited to answer an [online survey](#) in the scope of WP3. This reached an open rate of 87.5%.

2.9 Videos

At this stage, six promotional videos have been produced and uploaded to the EN-TRACK YouTube channel. Two videos have been produced to target the Building Owners Forum in the Catalan and Bulgarian context respectively. Hence, they have been produced with both English and Catalan/Bulgarian subtitles. According to the local EN-TRACK partners, the stakeholders in Catalan and Bulgaria must be reached in local languages. In addition to adding these videos to the EN-TRACK YouTube channel, local partners are sharing them on their channels to increase the outreach. Table 8 provides an overview of the videos produced and the number of views.

EnEffect has uploaded the Bulgarian version to their [YouTube channel](#). So far the communication around the Catalan version is being planned in the communication department of DTES and ICAEN but the video has already been shared on partners personal social media accounts.

Title	Partners	Language	Date	Views*	Summary
Interview with project coordinator	CIMNE- BEE Group & GECCO Global	English	Jan. 2021	80	A 3 minutes video interview where the project coordinator explains the purpose of the EN-TRACK project.

Title	Partners	Language	Date	Views*	Summary
Introductory Webinar	CIMNE-BEE Group, EP Group & GECO Global	English	May 2021	44	The recordings of the EN-TRACK introductory webinar
How can EN-TRACK help building owners?	ICAEN, DTES & GECO Global	English & English subtitles	Oct. 2021	34	A short video based on peer-to-peer communication in a Catalan context. Partners explain how EN-TRACK addresses the challenges they are facing.
How can EN-TRACK help building owners? Catalan	ICAEN, DTES & GECO Global	English & Catalan subtitles	Nov. 2021	9	The same as the above with Catalan text and subtitles
Know your buildings?	EnEffect & GECO Global	English & English subtitles	Nov. 2021	2	A short video based on peer-to-peer communication in a Bulgarian context. Partners explain how EN-TRACK addresses the challenges they are facing.
Know your buildings! Bulgarian	EnEffect & GECO Global	English & Bulgarian subtitles	Nov. 2021	32**	The same as the above with Bulgarian text and subtitles

Table 8

* Data extracted January 23, 2022.

**Including numbers from the [YouTube channel](#) of the Bulgarian project partner EnEffect.

2.10 Posters and flyers

At the beginning of the project, two posters targeting the key stakeholder categories, that is, the financial institutions and the building owners and operators, were designed (see D7.2). To target this communication even more, the poster addressing building owners and operators were translated to Catalan and Bulgarian (Figure 2), the two languages of the pilot sites.

Figure 2

Figure 3

The posters were also redesigned to fit into PowerPoint presentations to be used by partners when presenting the project at events (see Figure 3).

To target the financial institutions and investors a flyer (see Figure 4) integrating the key messages (see D7.2 for further details) to this stakeholder category was designed.

Figure 4

INTRODUCING EN-TRACK

DE-RISKING SUSTAINABLE INVESTMENTS

THE GOAL OF EN-TRACK IS TO CREATE A ONE-STOP-SHOP PLATFORM WITH STANDARDIZED DATA RELATED TO THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY PERFORMANCE OF THE PUBLIC AND PRIVATE BUILDING STOCK.

ABOUT EN-TRACK

HOW CAN WE HELP YOU WITH SUSTAINABLE INVESTMENTS?

Most of the information that is needed to make financing of energy efficiency a mainstream activity already exists. The problem is that it is inaccessible, poorly organized, or simply unlocated.

The EN-TRACK process is designed to make data input simpler, more attractive, and cost-effective, all while making the outputs more valuable by making them compatible with emerging market leader applications such as DEEP, eQuad and EnerInvest.

WITH EN-TRACK YOU GET

- Easily accessible standardized data in a one-stop shop platform.
- A clear overview of your data to facilitate benchmarking and comparisons.
- Access to make informed decisions based on empirical data.

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The aim was to distribute the printed version at the Sustainable Places 2021 event. However, due to force majeure it was held back in the airport and was not located before the event ended. As it is not an event specific flyer it will be distributed at the earliest opportunity.

3 Online presence

This section provides a status of the online activities, including website activity and social media presence.

3.1 Website

The KPIs stated in the Grant Agreement are the number of page views (500 per year) and the number of unique users (1500 in total by M36). To monitor the website activity, Monster Insights Pro and Google Analytics was installed in November 2021. Unfortunately, data isn't available for the period from the launch of the website in February 2021 and until November 7, 2021. The total number of unique users is 155 and the number of page views accounts to 632. The number of unique users is below the

total project target, as to be expected at this early stage, but in line with expectations. The number of page views is performing well.

Since the launch of the website in M4, it has been updated regularly. On the Help Desk pages targeting [FIF](#) and [BOF](#) respectively, the programmes for the quarterly FIF and BOF events have been added. Furthermore, the FAQ sections have been populated with preliminary questions, making it an interactive and engaging website. In addition, the [news section](#) now has 9 articles in total, including e.g., interviews, introductions to published deliverables and scientific articles and updates on project progress.

3.2 LinkedIn

Table 9 shows the status of the KPIs for the project's LinkedIn account. KPIs reached are marked in **green**, others in **red**. Data is extracted January 23, 2022. The number for LinkedIn followers has reached 56.7% of the KPI for M36. This is very promising, given that EN-TRACK is not even half-way through the project timeline, and indicates that the project is performing well in this respect. It is reasonable to assume that the M36 KPI, supported by the upcoming promotion activities, supported by all consortium partners.

LinkedIn community	N° of followers	68	120 in total by M36
	N° of news published	35	30 in total by M36

Table 9

3.3 Twitter

The status of the KPIs for the project's Twitter account is displayed in Table 10. KPIs reached are marked in **green**, others in **red**. Data is extracted January 23, 2022. The only KPI for Twitter which hasn't been reached by now, is the number of tweets. This, as with previous M36 KPIs, is logical and is due to the project being only half-way through the timeline.

Twitter community	N° of followers	152	80 per year
	N° of tweets published	45	250 in total by M36

	Total N° of tweet impressions	31.183	300 in total by M36
	N° of engagements (retweet, like, link click)	706	350 in total by M36

Table 10

3.4 YouTube

The status of the KPIs for the project's YouTube account is displayed in Table 11. KPIs reached are marked in **green**, others in **red**. Data is extracted January 23, 2022.

YouTube community	N° of views on project video	201 in total = 34 per video	25 per video
	N° of videos published	6	2 in total by M36

Table 11

3.5 ENLIT Europe

EN-TRACK is featured in the Enlit Europe platform and is now present in the [EU projects zone](#), thus gaining visibility in the Enlit EU Projects Marketplace and gaining presence in networking opportunities with relevant stakeholders, with whom the project consortium aims to hold conversations and interactions that support the development and exploitation of the EN-TRACK platform.

4 KPI Monitoring

Table 12 gives a total overview of the KPIs related to the communication and dissemination activities of the EN-TRACK project. As can be seen, many of the KPIs have already been reached by M15 of the project, especially with regards to the online outreach activities. This is good news and very encouraging. Other activities such as workshops and webinars are currently being planned based on a workshop amongst

consortium partners, held in M15. These activities add content to the Detailed Activity Planning which is the overall roadmap developed in the beginning of the project (see D7.3), to ensure that all KPIs are reached by the end of the project. The Detailed Activity Planning is stored at the shared online repository and updated regularly. The planning of communication and dissemination activities will continue to take place in the scope of the monthly Communication and Stakeholder Board meetings where all consortium partners are present.

With regards to the number of website users, this number is expected to rise significantly once the EN-TRACK platform is launched partly as a result of increased publicity and promotion activities, and also as a result of the use of the HelpDesk.

Dissemination activities	Dissemination KPI	Status M1-M15	Target
Project website	N° of unique users	155	1,500 total in by M36
	N° of pageviews	632	500 per year
Newsletter	N° of newsletter subscriptions through the website	87*	1,500 in total by M36
	N° of newsletters sent	2	2 per year
	N° of subscribers (outside consortium)	87	1,000 in total by M36
	Open rate	33.7%	50%
Events	N° of events with the EN-TRACK active presence	2	5 per year

Dissemination activities	Dissemination KPI	Status M1-M15	Target
	N° of events with EN-TRACK presentations	8	3 per year
	N° of workshops targeting EN-TRACK stakeholders	None yet	4 by M36
	N° of attendees to EN-TRACK workshops	None yet	10 per workshop
Technical publications	N° of press releases and/or articles published in the local, national or EU level journals	4	2 per year
	Estimated numbers of readers of the article and/or media releases.	776 <i>full-text views</i> **	120 in total by M36
Promotion materials	Quantity of promotional materials produced	9	5 per year
Interaction with H2020 projects / initiatives	N° of project synergies developed	2	10 in total by M36
	N° of joint workshops	None yet	2 in total by M36

Dissemination activities	Dissemination KPI	Status M1-M15	Target
Twitter community	N° of followers	152	80 per year
	N° of tweets published	45	250 in total by M36
	Total N° of tweet impressions	31.183	300 in total by M36
	N° of engagements (retweet, like, link click)	706	350 in total by M36
LinkedIn community	N° of subscribers	68	120 in total by M36
	N° of news published	35	30 in total by M36
YouTube community	N° of views on project video	201 in total = 34 per video	25 per video
	N° of videos published	6	2 in total by M36

Table 12

*The online community to which the EN-TRACK newsletter is sent to, currently accounts for 87 stakeholders. However, the newsletter is also promoted via the social media accounts of the project, its Horizon 2020 sister projects and the social media accounts of the consortium partners. In addition to this, BEE-Group CIMNE shares the newsletter with its 690 subscribers in Catalan, Spanish and English. EnEffect also shared the newsletter via the Municipal Energy Efficiency Network – EcoEnergy. The newsletter is sent to over 650 recipients. Up to now there is 5 publications in January, February, March, May and October.

** This number includes the published scientific articles (section 2.5). It is unfortunately not possible to track the number of readers for the articles published on BuildUp and the EN-TRACK website. In addition to these articles, the public deliverables currently account for 64 unique downloads.

5 Conclusions

In the period M1-M15 of the project, the dissemination and communication efforts have successfully facilitated internal and external interactions that helped create awareness around the project. An evaluation of the KPI targets showed that EN-TRACK is very well on track with most KPIs. Where it is not the case, necessary mitigation actions have been planned and a roadmap for coming dissemination and communication activities has been created to ensure that all KPIs will be reached and to support the exploitation potential of the project. This includes an increased collaboration with sister projects (8), webinars (4), workshops (4), publications and presentations at relevant events and fairs. This work will be supported by the Communication and Stakeholder Board meetings with the continued effort of all consortium partners.

